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(54) Title of the invention : MULTIWALL CARBON NANOTUBE, GRAPHENE AND JUTE MAT FIBRE REINFORCED EPOXY NANOCOMPOSITES

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(57) Abstract :

The growth of a civilization that is pollution-free and good for the environment has been made possible by the contemporary world and the shifting demands it places on society. In this scenario, one of the most viable solutions is the use of natural fibre polymer composites. When it comes to the processing of materials, natural fibres have a number of advantages over synthetic materials, low cost, easily available and provide high-quality characteristics. In this research Jute mat fibre with multi-wall carbon nanotube (MWCNT) and Graphene (Gr) are used as reinforcing material in the epoxy matrix and investigate the best possible combination of reinforcement which have the best impact properties.

Fig:1

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